

Grain quality

Physical and milling characters of popular Maruteru rice varieties

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We evaluated the physical and milling characters of eight rainfed lowland rice varieties commonly grown in Andhra Pradesh and parts of Maharashtra,

Karnataka, and Orissa, India. Sampling was done 1 mo after harvest; grain had 14% moisture content.

The 1,000-grain weight of Vijetha was heaviest (see table). All have medium-shaped grain and medium-length grain, extra for Vijetha, which has long grain.

The brown rice recovery was higher for MTU4870 and Krishnaveni compared with other varieties. The milled rice recovery was highest for MTU4870.

The bran and germ percentage for Nandi was highest (10.1) followed by that for Krishnaveni (9.4) and Chaitanya (9.1). Among these varieties, head rice recovery was highest in MTU4870. Except for Swarna and Chaitanya, all other varieties yielded more than the acceptable head rice recovery of 60% (see table). Broken rice were lowest in Vijetha (3.4%) and highest in Swarna (7.6%). ■

Physical and milling characters of popular rice varieties. Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, India. 1995.

Variety	Physical characters					Milling characters (%)							
	Duration (d)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Grain thickness (mm)	L-B ratio	Grain length	Grain shape	1000-grain weight (g)	Brown rice	Bran and germ	Milled rice recovery	Broken rice	Head rice recovery
Swarna MTU7029	150	5.77	2.24	1.72	2.57	Medium	Medium	19.90	75.50	8.90	66.60	7.61	58.99
Pratibha MTU5293	165	6.35	2.16	1.70	2.94	Medium	Medium	20.60	74.50	6.30	68.20	4.30	63.90
Vajram MTU5249	150	6.13	2.31	1.71	2.64	Medium	Medium	21.10	76.60	7.40	69.20	5.22	63.98
Nandi MTU5182	150	6.10	2.25	1.75	2.72	Medium	Medium	21.10	76.70	10.10	66.60	5.50	61.10
Chaitanya MTU2067	150	5.81	2.35	1.62	2.46	Medium	Medium	20.90	70.70	9.10	61.60	6.50	55.10
Krishnaveni MTU2077	150	5.69	2.24	1.72	2.54	Medium	Medium	20.20	77.10	9.40	67.70	5.40	62.30
Vijetha MTU 1001	140	6.63	2.37	1.85	2.80	Long	Medium	27.50	74.50	8.70	65.80	3.40	62.40
MTU4870	150	5.88	2.28	1.79	2.57	Medium	Medium	22.00	77.20	6.30	70.90	4.60	66.30
X		6.05	2.28	1.73	2.67			21.60	75.38	8.28	67.08	5.32	61.76
SD		0.32	0.07	0.07	0.15			2.44	2.17	1.44	2.75	1.31	3.45
CV		5.34	2.98	3.89	5.74			4.50	2.88	17.34	4.10	24.56	5.58

Variability of quality indices in aromatic rice germplasm

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Aromatic rice varieties are generally preferred over nonaromatic types and therefore earn premium prices. Among the aromatics, those with long slender grains (length >6.5 mm and breadth <2.0 mm) and high lengthwise volume expansion after cooking are popularly called basmati rice. These varieties have helped countries such as India, Pakistan, and Thailand earn considerable foreign exchange.

We evaluated 356 traditional aromatic rice varieties for eight grain and

cooking characteristics: amylose content (AC), gelatinization temperature (GT) as indicated by the alkali spreading score, gel consistency (GC), milled rice kernel length (KL), kernel breadth (KB), kernel length-breadth ratio (L/B), kernel elongation after cooking (KE) (length of cooked rice divided by

original kernel length using the average of 10 unbroken milled rice kernels), and 1,000-grain weight (WT).

Wide variation was observed for all the characteristics, with the maximum being for GC followed by WT and AC. Most of the aromatic varieties from India, Myanmar, Nepal, and Pakistan

Table 1. Varieties (no.) in different groups based on quality indices.

Quality index	Very low	Low	Intermediate	High
Amylose content (%)	2.5-9.0	9.0-20.0	20.1-25.0	>25.0
	27	169	155	5
Gelatinization temperature (Alkali spreading score)	6&7	-	4 & 5	1&3
	54		273	29
Gel consistency (mm)	-	0-40	41-60	>60
		77	148	131
Kernel elongation	1.31-1.60	1.61-1.80	1.81-2.0	>2.0
	66	100	101	69
Length-breadth ratio	1.3-2.0	2.01-3.0	3.01-4.0	>4.01
	44	140	159	13